

CHEMICAL EXAMINATION OF THE SEEDS OF *SOLANUM XANTHOCARPUM*, (SCHARD AND WENDLE). PART II. THE CONSTITUENTS.

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The benzene extract of the seeds of *Solanum xanthocarpum* yields (i) semi-drying oil, (ii) a lactone, $C_{22}H_{42}O_7$, m. p. 78° and (iii) a sterol, carpesterol, $C_{28}H_{54}O_4$, m. p. 216° $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -86^\circ$ in CH_2Cl_2 . The alcoholic percolate of the defatted seeds gives in addition to the lactone, a gluco-alkaloid, $C_{44}H_{74}O_4N_2$, m. p. 272° , $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +83.53^\circ$ which on acid hydrolysis gives the aglucone, solanacarpigenin, $C_{22}H_{34}O_2N_2$, m. p. 96° $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +88.7^\circ$ and glucose, rhamnose and potassium chloride.

Solanum xanthocarpum as a whole plant was examined by Pendse and Dutt (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1932, 20, 663) but they could not isolate any alkaloid although they reported the presence of it in the plant in traces. They attributed the physiological activity of the whole plant to potassium nitrate which is present in it to the extent of 1.6%.

Saiyed and Kanga (*Proc. Indian Sci. Congress*, 1934, p. 44) reported the isolation of a gluco-alkaloid (m. p. 245°) from the seeds of the plant by petrol extraction. In addition to this they also extracted two more basic substances melting at 265° and 196° . In a later communication (*Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1936, 4A, 255) the same authors have given the results of the examination in detail, where they claim to have isolated a gluco-alkaloid *solanacarpine* ($C_{44}H_{77}O_{19}N$), m.p. $288-89^\circ$ (decomp.) in white flat needles, and an alkaloid called *solanacarpidine* ($C_{26}H_{43}O_3N$), m. p. $197-98^\circ$, in the form of shining plates, from the alcoholic extract of the fruit. They have also isolated a sterol named by them *carpesterol*, m. p. 248° , which they had previously reported as a gluco-alkaloid, and a fixed oil from the petrol extract of the fruit.

Amongst the products of hydrolysis of the above gluco-alkaloid ($C_{44}H_{77}O_{19}N$) they have identified the alkaloid $C_{26}H_{43}O_3N$, and glucose, rhamnose and galactose, the presence of the latter being doubtful. They also state that the sugar-free alkaloid ($C_{26}H_{43}O_3N$) is present in the fruit as such, although they have not recorded any method for the separation of the two.

The present investigation was already in progress when the above paper by Saiyed and Kanga was published. On account of the great

medicinal importance of the plant in the indigenous system of medicines, and also because of the fact that one of the present authors had already tackled the whole plant before, it was highly desirable that the investigation on the seeds of the plant should be more thoroughly carried out.

In a previous communication Gupta and Dutt (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 13, 613) in course of their investigation on the chemical constituents of the seeds of *Solanum xanthocarpum*, isolated from the benzene extract, a fixed oil which on standing deposited some crystalline substance. In the present paper, the systematic chemical analysis of this substance as well as the isolation and examination of the other constituents of the seeds are given.

The above mentioned crystalline substance on further treatment was separated into a sterol, *carpsterol* (m.p. 248°) isolated by the previous workers, with a molecular formula $C_{36}H_{54}O_4$, and another microcrystalline substance ($C_{28}H_{42}O_7$, m.p. 78°) which exhibited all the characteristic properties of the $\Delta^{\alpha\beta}$ -unsaturated lactones.

The present authors have also isolated from the alcoholic extract some more of the lactone stated above, and also a gluco-alkaloid, $C_{44}H_{74}O_{11}N_2$, m.p. 272° crystallising in snow-white needles, and not the sugar-free alkaloid as the previous authors claim. Besides that, the present alkaloid is found to contain two atoms of nitrogen in the molecule instead of one atom as found by the previous workers. An alkaloid, $C_{32}H_{54}O_2N_2$, m.p. 196°, together with glucose and rhamnose have been identified as the products of hydrolysis of the gluco-alkaloid by mineral acids. There is also obtained some inorganic salt which has been identified as potassium chloride.

Further examination of the seeds of the plant for the sugar-free alkaloid has revealed the interesting fact that it is not present in the seeds as such, and the fact that the previous workers isolated it from the seeds may be due to the hydrolysing effect of hydrogen sulphide which they used in course of the isolation.

Between the two methods, namely the lead salt method, and the chromate salt method that have been worked up for the isolation of the gluco-alkaloid, the latter is most satisfactory and convenient, and the yield of the gluco-alkaloid is also quite good. Unlike the former, in the latter process no resinification or hydrolysis of the gluco-alkaloid takes place and the gluco-alkaloid is obtained in a pure condition.

Contrary to the statement of Saiyed and Kanga (*loc. cit.*) we find that the gluco-alkaloid can not be crystallised from pure ethyl alcohol, as it does not separate from dilute solution, and from hot concentrated solution it

separates as a translucent jelly on cooling. It has been crystallised by the present authors from a mixture of alcohol and ether.

A sample of the alkaloid has been sent to the Tropical School of Medicine, Calcutta for physiological investigation. Further work on the constitution of the alkaloid is in progress and will be dealt with in a separate communication.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Preliminary Experiments.—After a series of preliminary experiments, 8.2 kg. of the powdered and oil-free seeds were percolated 6 times with hot 98% ethyl alcohol in two lots. The combined percolates were concentrated to half their original volume at the ordinary pressure and allowed to stand overnight, when a quantity of colourless crystalline matter was deposited which was filtered off and identified as potassium chloride. The filtrate was further concentrated under diminished pressure below 40° and the resulting brownish yellow syrup completely dried in a vacuum desiccator over calcium chloride. The viscid residue was finally freed from traces of oil by thorough agitation with petroleum ether.

Isolation of the Gluco-alkaloid Solanacarpine.—The above dried residue was extracted with 5% acetic acid a number of times until the last extract gave no appreciable precipitate with ammonia; the voluminous precipitate was filtered off and dried. This was then further extracted with 2% dilute hydrochloric acid and the filtered extract basified with ammonia when a dirty grey precipitate was obtained which was filtered off, washed and dried. The crude alkaloid thus obtained could not be crystallised from any solvent, and the only insoluble salts that could be obtained from it were the lead salt and the chromate salt. As the lead compound necessitated the use of hydrogen sulphide for its decomposition, which invariably complicated matters by extensive hydrolysis of the gluco-alkaloid, the chromate salt was found to be the most suitable for the purification of the gluco-alkaloid. A solution of potassium chromate was added to dilute acetic acid solution of the crude alkaloid, and the yellow amorphous voluminous precipitate of the chromate was filtered off, washed with water and then crystallised from alcohol. The crystalline chromate was then suspended in water and decomposed with excess of aqueous ammonia, when a dirty white precipitate of the impure gluco-alkaloid was obtained. This was dissolved in alcohol and boiled with animal charcoal and the alcoholic filtrate concentrated when an almost colourless translucent jelly was ob-

tained. On allowing to stand much of the mother liquor separated from the stiff translucent material and the latter was filtered off and dried. The dried product was then dissolved in alcohol and ether gradually added, when most of the impurities separated in the form of a brownish viscous mass. The product was filtered at this stage and more ether added to the filtrate until a slight turbidity appeared. On allowing to stand, the gluco-alkaloid separated in the form of glistening colourless curved needles, which under the microscope have a characteristic feathery appearance. On heating the substance begins to darken in colour at 249° , becomes completely brown at 262° and melts at 272° . It is optically active, $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +83.5^{\circ}$. The yield of the gluco-alkaloid was 1.41% on the weight of the dried seeds. (Found : C, 65.23, 65.05, 64.96 ; H, 8.95, 9.00, 9.28 ; N, 3.50, 3.14. $C_{14}H_{14}O_{11}N_2$ requires C, 65.50 ; H, 9.18 ; N, 3.59 per cent).

The gluco-alkaloid is soluble in water and dilute acids. It is readily soluble in ethyl and methyl alcohol, chloroform and acetone, sparingly soluble in ethyl acetate, and insoluble in benzene, ether and petroleum ether. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a bright yellow colour which gradually changes to orange and red, and on keeping becomes dark brown. It dissolves with a yellow colour in cold concentrated nitric acid which remains unchanged on standing.

Hydrolysis of the Gluco-alkaloid and Isolation of the Aglucone: Solanacarpigenin.—The chromate salt of the gluco-alkaloid (50 g.) was heated with excess of 5% hydrochloric acid under reflux for 3 hours on a boiling water-bath. The separated dirty solid was filtered, washed, dried and decomposed with ammonia in alcoholic solution. After filtration, the liquid was concentrated, when the aglucone separated in the form of a brown crystalline mass. This was filtered off, the residue extracted with ether, and the ethereal extract evaporated. The colourless crystalline mass was then recrystallised from alcohol as glistening snow-white star-shaped prisms, m.p. 196° . The yield of the alkaloid was 0.35% on the weight of the dry seeds. (Found : C, 76.49, 76.96 ; H, 10.63, 10.94 ; N, 5.50, 5.78. $C_{32}H_{54}O_2N_2$ requires C, 77.10 ; H, 10.84 ; N, 5.62 per cent).

This aglucone has solubilities quite similar to the gluco-alkaloid. It is optically active, $[\alpha]_D^{20} = +88.79^{\circ}$. With concentrated sulphuric acid it produces a bright yellow colouration, which gradually turns orange, then red and finally dark brown. On gradually adding water the colouration changes to green, then blue, then yellow and ultimately disappears. With concentrated nitric acid it produces a colouration similar to the gluco-alkaloid.

The filtrate left after the acid hydrolysis of the chromate salt of the gluco-alkaloid and removal of the aglucone, contained reducing sugars which were converted into their mixed osazones and separated by repeated crystallisations from acetone in which they had different solubilities. In this way the presence of glucose and rhamnose was confirmed.

Isolation of the Lactone : Solanocarpone.

(a) *From the Oil-free Seed.*—The residue left after treatment with 5% acetic acid in course of isolation of solanacarpine was digested with caustic soda in the cold a number of times, and the combined extracts left overnight whereby some resinous impurities settled down which were filtered off. The filtrate on acidification with dilute hydrochloric acid deposited the lactone as a brown precipitate which on crystallisation from methyl alcohol was obtained in cream coloured microscopic needles, m.p. 78°.

(b) *From the Oil.*—The oil on allowing to stand for about a month deposited some crystalline matter which was filtered off, washed with petroleum ether, dried and recrystallised from benzene until free from stickiness. The substance was then repeatedly extracted with warm ethyl alcohol until nothing further was extracted. The combined extract on cooling deposited the lactone as a brown amorphous powder which on crystallisation from boiling absolute alcohol was obtained as a cream coloured mass of microscopic needles, m.p. 78°, yield 2.1 g. or 0.12% on the weight of the dry seeds. [Found : C, 68.40, 68.86 ; H, 9.29, 9.00 ; M.W. (ebullioscopic in ethyl alcohol), 460,553. $C_{28}H_{42}O_7$ requires C, 68.57 ; H, 8.57 per cent. M.W. 490].

The substance shows all the characteristic properties of $\Delta^{\alpha,\beta}$ -unsaturated lactones. It dissolves easily in benzene, acetone, ethyl acetate, chloroform and phenol; it is slightly soluble in methyl and ethyl alcohol and is insoluble in ether, petroleum ether and water. It dissolves in alcoholic caustic soda or potash with an intense yellow colouration, from which it is precipitated unchanged on acidification. It quickly decolourises a solution of bromine in chloroform and also an alkaline and acidic solution of potassium permanganate. It gives a positive Salkowski's reaction, i.e., a solution of the lactone in chloroform gives with concentrated sulphuric acid a red and finally a green colouration. A solution of the lactone in chloroform on treatment with acetic anhydride followed by concentrated sulphuric acid gives a fine violet colouration. With concentrated sulphuric acid it produces an intense yellow colour which finally changes to deep red. With

concentrated nitric acid it develops a yellow colour on heating. It gives a white precipitate with lead acetate, but no precipitate or colouration with silver nitrate or ferric chloride. With Tollen's reagent a light yellow colouration is formed which slowly changes to brown and then a gradual reduction takes place. With an alkaline solution of sodium nitroprusside it gives no colouration.

Isolation of a Carpenterol from the Oil.—The crystalline deposit from the oil after separation of the above lactone, was dissolved in boiling ethyl alcohol and on cooling the sterol separated in the form of shining white plates, m.p. 248°, $[\alpha]_D^{20} = -80^\circ$. (Found : C, 78.46, 78.1; H, 10.1, 9.4. $C_{36}H_{54}O_4$ requires C, 78.54; H, 9.81 per cent).

The substance is fairly soluble in boiling ethyl and methyl alcohol, sparingly soluble in hot benzene, chloroform and acetone and very sparingly soluble in ether and petroleum ether. It gives all the characteristic colour reactions of a sterol.

The *acetyl* derivative was obtained by the usual methods and it crystallised from alcohol in colourless silky needles, m.p. 194°. (Found : C, 77.20, 76.98; H, 9.91, 10.12. $C_{38}H_{56}O_5$ requires C, 77.03; H, 9.5 per cent).

The *benzoyl* derivative was obtained by benzylation with benzoyl chloride and pyridine in the usual manner and crystallised from ethyl alcohol in colourless silky needles, m.p. 216°. (Found : C, 78.52; H, 9.12. $C_{43}H_{58}O_5$ requires C, 78.89; H, 8.86 per cent).

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